

Japanese Taro/Satoimo's (*Colocasia Esculenta* Var *Antiquorum*). potential and opportunities as alternative food to support food security

Heni Purwaningsih, Irawati, Nurdeana C and Umi Pudji Astuti
Yogyakarta Assessment Institute for Agriculture Technology
Coessponding author : heny_yk@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

*Food security is the condition of fulfilling food for households which is reflected in the availability of adequate food, both in quantity/quality, safe and evenly distributed and affordable. Food security for an area is very important. Given that food is a basic need and is a human right. Food in this study is Japanese tuber/satoimo (*Colocasia esculenta* var *antiquorum* L). With sufficient food needs that will produce good food security as well. Japanese taro / Satoimo is one of the alternative foods that can replace rice. The superiority of Satoimo can be cultivated on open land or under other plant stands. Based on the results of the research, Satoimo can grow shaded up to 70% . Satoimo productivity reaches 30,000 kg/ha with a higher selling price compared to other taro. Satoimo has nutrients that are beneficial to health, including protein, vitamin A, vitamin C, minerals, and hyluronic acid. Satoimo fresh is a source of calcium and calories but with low carbohydrate and zero sugar content and well consumed as a food diet and is very good for diabetics Based on the results of the business feasibility analysis, satoimo cultivation has a normal R/C value of 2.3-2.9 means that it is worth developing.*

Keywords: *Satoimo, potential and opportunities, alternative food, food security*

INTRODUCTION

Food security according to Regulation No.7 in 1996 concerning food security, is the condition of fulfilling food for every household, which is reflected in the availability of sufficient food, both quantity and quality, safe, equitable, and affordable. Understanding of food security includes macro aspects, namely the availability of adequate food; and at the same time micro aspects, namely the fulfillment of the food needs of each household to live a healthy and active life.

Food security is the basic pillar of economic development and community welfare (Azahari, 2008). The realization of food security is pursued through some attempts, i.e. food diversification (Lastinawati, 2010). Food diversification efforts have been initiated since 1970. Food diversification program is implemented in accordance with Presidential Regulation no. 22 in which accelerates the diversification of food consumption based on local

resources (Permentan, 2016). The problem of food diversification is the imbalance between the rapid increase of population and the provision of food production from agricultural products. Production of various types of food in a food diversification program cannot be generated in all regions and cannot be produced at any time (Rachman and H.P.S. 2001). At the national level, food security is defined as the ability of a nation to guarantee that all its inhabitants get adequate food, adequate quality, safe, and is based on optimizing utilization and based on the diversity of local resources.

One type of non-rice food commodity that has good value and economic prospects is Japanese Taro Satoimo (*Colocasia esculenta var antiquorum* L) or known as Taro Potato. This one foodstuff has now become one of the main foodstuffs for the majority of the Japanese population as a substitute for rice and potatoes. They consider that rice and potatoes contain too much carbohydrate and sugar. Many Japanese people divert their consumption to this type of taro Japanese. Taro has actually entered Indonesia for a long time, namely during the Japanese occupation in period of 1942 - 1945. The food insecurity situation that hit almost all parts of Indonesia at that time, forced the Japanese occupation government to bring the original sakura country food commodities into Indonesia. The population who at that time was still colonized and then forced to plant this taro, is not to meet the food needs of the colonized nation, but for food reserves for the Japanese population in their country, only low quality taro could be consumed by the Indonesian people. After independence, Japanese taro was then forgotten, because it was not a staple food for most of the Indonesian population and the market prospect at that time was unclear, as well as in its home country, these food-producing plants were also not a priority in the development of their agriculture. Only in 1980s, the Japanese government again promoted the cultivation of this commodity after various studies that proved that Japanese taro could not only be an alternative food that contains high protein and calories but having low carbohydrate and sugar content, so that it is safe for the sufferer or those who are potentially diabetic, besides having benefits other than just as food.

Japanese taro/Satoimo plants are tuber plants that have great potential for cultivation in Indonesia. Currently, the price of taro tubers is relatively higher than the price of other types of taro tubers (Taufik, 2015). This is due to the high utilization of taro tubers in the field of Japanese pharmaceutical and taro cultivation is still limited so that the taro tubers produced is still small. The current breeding of jasmine taro is still done vegetatively using tubers. Japanese taro cultivation on a large scale requires seeds in large quantities so needed an efficient and simple way in providing taro seeds japan.

Japanese taro can be used as food, animal feed, pharmaceutical industry raw materials and cosmetics. Taro is a staple food in West Sumatra and West

Papua, and processed taro flour with a mixture of wheat flour is processed into baby food (United States), baking (Philippines), bread (Brazil), chips and dodol (Indonesia) (Lingga et al., 1990). Utilization of taro as the fulfillment of the needs of the community needs to be balanced with the increase of taro cultivation. Nationally there is no data on taro production in Indonesia.

The demand for Japanese taro (Satoimo) that is relatively high primarily from other countries is an export opportunity to Japan. Many demand for Japanese taro because of the advantages possessed. The aim of this paper is to provide information on the production, nutritional value and economic analysis of taro to know the opportunities Japanese taro/satoimo as an export commodity.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Cultivation Technique

Satoimo/Japanese taro cultivation is simple and easy to be practiced because it is almost suitable in all regions in Indonesia. Satoimo cultivation can be done in farm, sandy soil or under shading. The location of cultivation greatly determines the production of Satoimo. The cultivation technique can be followed as:

1. Land Arrangement (making of bunds) The length of bunds can be adjusted to the existing land area, while the width of 120 cm and the height of 15 cm. making a planting hole with a distance of 60 cm x 40 cm with a diameter of 25 cm and a depth of 15 cm.
2. Fertilized with Manure at the planting hole about 500gr per hole
3. Satoimo that has grown two-leaved and has rooted (healthy condition), placed on the planting hole with a depth of surface maximum of 10 cm. Further dumped with soil around the hole and watered.
4. Watering every day morning and evening if needed in accordance with the condition of soil moisture around the plant.
5. Giving fertilizer back every plant at plant age 1 month after planting sprinkled 10 cm - 20 cm from the stem of the plant (circular) and immediately dumped the surrounding land,
6. Cleaning of weeds and ground beds of soil as high as 5 -10 cm from the base of the stem of the plant itself, also done in case of erosion due to rain.
7. Harvesting can be done 5-6 months after planting.

Productivity of Satoimo

The productivity of satoimo in Playen Subdistrict of Gunungkidul Regency is highly depend on the soil type. According to Purwaningsih and Irawati (2103), Satoimo can grow under shading up to 70%. Potential production

in sandy soil is higher (3.4 kg / m²) than in the farm (2.04 kg / m²) with various characteristics. Productivity at others province is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Production and productivity of satoimo commodity of in Kepahiang Regency of Bengkulu Province in 2013.

Number	Village	Height (mdpl)	Land area (Ha)	Product (kg)	Productivity (kg/Ha)
1.	Tebat Monok	520	1	12.400	12.400
2.	Bumi Sari	660	0,5	6.650	13.300
3.	Pematang Donok	780	0,5	7.300	14.600
4.	Suka Sari	1.100	5	74.500	14.900

Source : Department of Agriculture of Kepahiang Regency, 2013

Production and Productivity of Satoimo Farming During the Planting Season (6 months) show in the table 2.

Table 2. Production and productivity per ha

Description	Amount	Average
Land area (Ha)	5,65	0,23
Product (Kg) :	81.622	
a. Every farmer (Kg)		3.265
b. Each plant(Kg)		3,40
Productivity (Kg/Ha)	361.640	14.466

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Table 2. showed that the cultivation of taro Satoimo in 0.23 hectares can get a production of 81,622 kg or average of 3,265 kg each farmer with productivity of 361,640 kg/ha or an average of 14,466 kg/ ha per farmers.

Nutrition Content

The advantages of Japanese taro (Satoimo) than others taro, are economic value, high nutrient content, and low carbohydrate content. Compared with other food commodities, satoimo is recommended for diabetics. Nutritional content of taro tuber jasmine and some other food commodities can be seen in Table 3. Satoimo contains higher fiber (16.8%) and calorie (92.30%) compared with others such as potato, rice and wheat.

Table 3. The nutritional content of Japanese taro, potatoes, rice, and wheat.

Type of Nutrition	Satoimo	Potato	Rice	Wheat
Calories (Cal)	92,30	83,00	36,00	36,50
Protein (g)	2,38	2,00	6,80	8,90
Fat (g)	0,17	0,10	0,70	1,30
Carbohydrate	16,33	19,00	78,90	77,30
Calcium (mg)	9,00	11,00	6,00	16,00
Phosphorus (g)	5,00	56,00	140,00	106,00
Fiber (CF) %	16,18	-	-	-

Resource: Seameo Biotrop and Nectar

Based on the results of the research on the nutritional content of Japanese taro as shown in Table 4. The nutritional content of raw Satoimo, steamed and boiled is different which is caused by the heating process during denaturation or damage or deterioration of nutritional content. However, nutritional content can increase due to the heating process and the addition of water. The content of vitamin C is quite high in raw of taro, it is very good for maintaining eye health, repairing skin cell tissue, reducing the risk of heart disease, and preventing premature aging (as anti-aging).

Table 4. Composition of Nutrients Content in 100 grams of Japanese Taro

Komponen	Satuan	Raw Satoimo	Steamed	Boiled
Calorie	Kal	98	120	-
Protein	gr	1,9	1,5	1,17
Fat	gr	0,2	0,3	29,31
Carbohydrate	gr	23,7	28,2	0,026
Calcium	mg	28,0	31,0	-
Phosphorus	mg	61,0	63,0	-
Iron	mg	1,0	0,7	-
Vit. A	RE	3,0	0	-
Vit. C	mg	4,0	2,0	-
Vit. B1	mg	0,13	0,05	-
Water	ml	73,0	69,2	61,0
Edible parts	%	85,0	85,0	-

Source : Rawuh, 2008.

According to Purwaningsih and Irawati, (2013), the content of fat and amylose satoimo / safira flour is 0.56% and 11.10%, respectively. The high amylose content is very good for the diet, because theoretically high amylose levels eat high levels of dietary fiber. According to McEwan (2008), Satoimo contains several minerals, especially sodium (740 mg / 100g), magnesium (79-122 mg / 100g), (3.05 mg / 100g) and iron (2.07 mg / 100g).

Satoimo is a healthy and youthful secret in Japan that contains hyaluronic acid which is the main ingredient of cartilage joints, which helps improve the movement of the joints, reduce pain, strengthen connective tissue and not cause allergies. In addition, hyaluronic-acid is very active in the health of joints, eyesight, connective tissue (connective-tissue) also accelerate the process of wound healing and play a role in the formation of collagen (JETRO.1994)

Hyaluronic acid (HA) as a collagen forming agent is very useful to reduce wrinkles on the skin surface and simultaneously tighten and maintain elasticity. Collagen is useful for the body to maintain skin rejuvenation and camouflage skin wrinkles. Collagen will maintain the elasticity of connective tissue on the skin so that the skin can contract or expand without damaging any tissue. With age, the collagen content will decrease so that the softness and elasticity of the skin is also reduced.

Based on research, at the age of 25 years, the body will start losing collagen as much as 1.5 percent each year. Therefore collagen plays a very important for those who are aged over 25 years and above to restore the elasticity and suppleness of the skin. Collagen is a major protein forming in body tissues, ranging from skin, hair, nails, bones and teeth are composed of this one protein (Jetro, 1994).

Especially for the skin, collagen is the most vital element in maintaining skin regeneration process to stay young. In the absence of adequate collagen, the skin becomes wrinkled, dry, dull, and rough.

Collagen intake to meet the body's needs often got from foods that contain lots of protein. But sometimes nutritional intake from food is not enough to fight the damage and aging of the skin. Because the skin is very susceptible to damage and damaged skin should be replaced with new skin so as not dull and dry. One alternative treatment that can help the skin in minimizing damage is by adding collagen from the outside.

Market Opportunity

Satoimo / safira has a good enough market opportunities for both domestic and overseas. Satoimo in Indonesia is widely used for food industry, animal feed and cosmetics. According to Purwaningsih et al. (2014), Satoimo / Safiran is used to make flour and processed into several types of food such as cake (brownies) and pastries. Satoimo is also used in the manufacture of brownies substituted with wheat flour because Satoimo / Safiran flour does not have gluten content so it needs a flour that has a high gluten content such as wheat flour. Substitutes received by consumers are 50% wheat flour and 50% safira flour.

Almost 50% of Japan's population consume taro as a staple food other

than rice. So Japan's current needs reach \pm 360,000 tons per year (Otsubo, 1996), while production capacity in Japan continues to decline to 250,000 tons per year, due to limited land and climatic factors that do not allow farming throughout the year (JETRO, 1994).

Supply shortages of imported satoimo a large part of China, which reached 55,000-60,000 tons (Japan Imports / Exports). Therefore Japan is still short of satoimo supply of 40,000 - 45,000 tons per year. Indonesia has the potential to meet satoimo supply shortages to Japan, as it is an agrarian country with two seasons that can support agricultural activities throughout the year.

Advantndages of Satoimo

Satoimo fresh is a source of calsium and calories but low carbohydrate and zero sugar content is therefore well consumed as a diet food and is very good for diabetics. While Satoimo flour can be used as Jelly or drink for health, pureed baby food, cake and bread raw materials, mixing the flour as substitute for potatoes, wheat, pharmacy / drugs as capsules and tablets. Fiber as material mix of jelly, ice cream biscuit, soup, drink, fibrous pudding and drink for diet and diabetic.

Farming System Analysis

Farming system is an applied science that discusses or learns how to make or use resources efficiently in an agricultural enterprise. Farming is also an organization of nature, work and capital aimed at agricultural production (Pindrik, 2003). According to Makeham, J.P (1991) farming is a collection of natural resources contained therein used for agricultural production such as fertile soil, water, repairs done, sunlight, buildings erected on the land. This is confirmed by Mubyarto (1989) that farming as a place or part of the earth's surface where agriculture is organized by a certain farmer as a landowner or a paid manager.

According to Soekartawi 2006, to determine the farmers income from satoimo cultivation, simple tabulation analysis can be done, with function as follows:

$$\pi = TR-TC$$

Where :

π (Revenue) = Farmer net income (Rp / Ut)

TR (Total Revenue) = Total revenue (Rp / Ut)

TC (Total Cost) = Total Cost (Rp / Ut)

To know whether or not satoimo farming done Return Cost Ratio (R / C ratio) analysis

1. Production Cost is calculated by the following formula:

$$C = FC + VC$$

Where :

$$C \text{ (Cost)} = \text{Total Cost (Rp)}$$

$$VC \text{ (Variable Cost)} = \text{Variable Cost (Rp / Ut)}$$

$$FC \text{ (Fixed Cost)} = \text{Fixed Cost (Rp / Ut)}$$

Acceptance is production multiplied selling price by the formula as follows:

$$R \text{ (Revenue)} = P \times Y \text{ Revenue (Price) = Selling Price}$$

$$Y \text{ (Product)} = \text{Production (Kg / Ut) With the following criteria:}$$

R/C ratio

If $R / C \geq 1$, then commodity farming of satoimo economically feasible cultivated

If $R / C < 1$, then commodity farming of satoimo is economically unfeasible to cultivated.

Analysis of Farming

The results of the farming analysis show differences in the value of R / C and B / C in each region. Yogyakarta and other regions have R / C or B / C values that are not much different.

Table 5. Feasibility of Japanese taro / Satoimo farming in Nglipar, Playen, Gunungkidul, Yogyakarta

Description	Amount
Cost per tree (Rp)	2.700
Production per tree (kg)	1,5
Amount of tree population per hectare	20.000
Total cost per hectare (Rp)	2.700 x 20.000 = 54.000.000
Seed`prices	37 % x Rp 54.000.000,- = Rp 19.980.000,
Land rent per season	13 % x Rp 54.000.000,- = Rp 7.020.000
Labor planting and maintenance per season	3% x Rp 54.000.000,- = Rp 1.620.000
Production facilities	30 % x Rp 54.000.000,- = Rp 16.200.00,
Harvest and post harvest	12 % x Rp 54.000.000,- = Rp 6.480.000,-
Total cost (A)	Rp.54.000.000
Selling prices per kg	Rp 4.000
Production per hectare :	20.000 x 1,5 kg = 30.000 kg
Yield in the form of rupiah (B)	30.000 x Rp 4.000=Rp 120.000.000

Income (B - A)	Rp 66.000.000
<i>Feasibility analysis</i>	
BEP production	54.000.000 : 4.000 = 13.500 kg.
BEP price	54.000.000 : 30.000 = Rp 1.800,-/kg.
R/C	120.000.000 : 54.000.000 = 2,23
B/C	66.000.000 : 54.000.000 = 1.23

Source: Purwaningsih, H and Irawarti 2013

Analysis of the feasibility of Japanese taro / satoimo business in other areas during the harvest period of 5-6 months.

Description	Amount
Cost production per tree (Rp)	Rp. 2.100
Production per hectare	30.000 kg
Price per kg	Rp. 4.000
Revenue per hectare	30.000 x 4.000 = Rp. 120.000.000
Cost production per hectare	20.000 X Rp. 2.100 =Rp, 42.000.000
Net income	120.000.000 – 42.000.000 = Rp. 78.000.000
BEP Production	42.000.000 : 4.000 X 1 kg = 10.500 kg
BEP Price	42.000.000: 30.000 X Rp. 1 = 1.400/kg
R/C	120.000.000 : 42.000.000 = 2,9
B/C	78.000.000 : 42.000.000 = 1,9

Source : Website Services Laboratory - Seameo Biotrop, 2008

CONCLUSIONS

Japanese taro is one of alternative foods that contain beneficial nutrients for human health, and has the opportunity to be developed. R / C ratio of Japanese taro/ satoimo is 2.23-2.90 that means satoimo is feasible to be cultivated and provide benefits for farmers. Market opportunities for satoimo are very promising.

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